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SMART MOTORCYCLE HELMET: REAL-TIME CRASH DETECTION WITH EMERGENCY NOTIFICATION, TRACKER AND ANTI-THEFT SYSTEM USING INTERNET-OF-THINGS CLOUD BASED TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Buying a car entails a cost, not counting the day to day high price tag of gasoline. People are looking for viable means of transportation that is cost-effective and can move its way through traffic faster. In the Philippines, motorcycle was the answer to most people transportation needs. With the increasing number of a motorcycle rider in the Philippines safety is the utmost concern. Today technology plays a huge role on how this safety can be assured. We now see advances in connected devices. Devices can sense its surrounding through sensor attach to it. With this in mind, this study focuses on the development of a wearable device named Smart Motorcycle Helmet or simply Smart Helmet, whose main objective is to help motorcycle rider in times of emergency. Utilizing sensors such as alcohol level detector, crash/impact sensor, Internet connection thru 3G, accelerometer, Short Message Service (SMS) and cloud computing infrastructure connected to a Raspberry Pi Zero-W and integrating a separate Arduino board for the anti-theft tracking module is used to develop the propose Internet-of Things (IoT) device.

Using quantitative method and descriptive type research, the researchers validated the results from the inputs of the participant who tested the smart helmet during the alpha and beta testing process. Taking into account the ethical consideration of the volunteers, who will test the Smart Helmet. To ensure the reliability of the beta and alpha testing, ISO 25010 quality model was used for the assessment focusing on the device accuracy, efficiency and functionality. Based on the inputs and results gathered, the proposed Smart Helmet IoT device can be used as a tool in helping a motorcycle rider when an accident happens to inform the first-responder of the accident location and informing the family of the motorcycle rider.

KEYWORDS

Smart Helmet, Internet of Things, Sensors, Real-Time Crash Detection, Emergency Notification, Tracker, Anti-Theft System Cloud Based Technology

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A SURVEY ON SECURITY CHALLENGES OF VIRTUALIZATION TECHNOLOGY IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Virtualization has become a widely and attractive employed technology in cloud computing environments. Sharing of a single physical machine between multiple isolated virtual machines leading to a more optimized hardware usage, as well as make the migration and management of a virtual system more efficiently than its physical counterpart. Virtualization is a fundamental technology in a cloud environment. However, the presence of an additional abstraction layer among software and hardware causes new security issues. Security issues related to virtualization technology have become a significant concern for organizations due to arising some new security challenges.

This paper aims to identify the main challenges and risks of virtualization in cloud computing environments. Furthermore, it focuses on some common virtual-related threats and attacks affect the security of cloud computing.

The survey was conducted to obtain the views of the cloud stakeholders on virtualization vulnerabilities, threats, and approaches that can be used to overcome them.

Finally, we propose recommendations for improving security, and mitigating risks encounter virtualization that necessary to adopt secure cloud computing.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Virtualization, Security, Challenge, Risk

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BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

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